

**When Trade Agreements Are Gender-Friendly:
Impact on Women Empowerment using Firm Data**

**Fida KARAM
Chahir ZAKI**

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Fida Karam¹

Chahir Zaki²

Abstract

This paper studies the effect of gender-related provisions in Regional Trade Agreement on under-explored aspects of gender inequality at the plant level, namely the difference in the managerial and ownership status between the two genders. This topic is timely and critical as gender equality considerations are becoming more prominent in new trade agreements, recognizing to different extents that trade policies developed with a gender perspective can help overcome gender inequalities by creating new opportunities for women's equal representation in export jobs and entrepreneurship. We use the World Bank Enterprise Surveys that encompasses data on 195,000 firms in 155 countries in 56 manufacturing and services sectors, and the dataset on gender-related provisions in trade agreements from the World Trade Organization. Our results show that the total number of gender-related provisions in trade agreements, as well their location in articles and in annexes are positively associated with a higher probability of the firm to be owned or managed by a female. This result is robust whether the firm is an exporter, importer, or involved in the global value chain of the sector of interest. When differentiating countries by income level, we find that the positive effect of gender-related provisions in trade agreements on women empowerment holds only for developed countries, pointing out the importance of making South-South agreements more gender friendly.

KEYWORDS: Regional Trade Agreements, Women Empowerment, Firm Data.

JEL CLASSIFICATIONS: F13, F14, F15

¹Associate Professor, Department of Economics and Finance, Gulf University for Science and Technology, Kuwait; E-mail: Karam.f@gust.edu.kw

² Chaired Professor, University of Orléans and Laboratoire d'Economie d'Orléans and Professor, Faculty of Economics and Political Science, Cairo university, Egypt; E-mail: chahir.zaki@fepe.edu.eg

1. Introduction

In one of the unachieved dimensions of gender equality, one can highlight the double-edged effect of trade liberalization on women in their different economic roles as consumers, workers, and entrepreneurs. Women may simultaneously gain and lose from trade openness. They may gain as consumers through lower tariffs on imported consumption goods, but be harmed if they are employed in sectors competing with cheap imported products. They may have access to increased employment opportunities in export-oriented sectors and therefore higher income, but have limited opportunities for skills development. They may have opportunities to access new export markets as entrepreneurs and increase their earnings, but may fail to compete internationally due to limited access to finance and networks (UNCTAD 2022). The mixed impact of trade on women have led policymakers to include gender-related considerations in regional trade agreements (RTA), as an affirmation of the country's commitment to reduce gender inequality through trade policy.

How effective are those gender-related provisions in promoting gender equality? The current paper investigates the effect of those provisions on under-explored aspects of gender inequality at the plant level, namely the difference in the managerial and ownership status between the two genders. This topic is timely and critical, not only because the number of RTAs with gender-related provisions increased significantly after 2016 (Monteiro, 2021), but also because the level of detail in such provisions has expanded over time, increasing the recognition of gender issues in trade policymaking. According to Monteiro (2021), 13% of the countries that negotiated RTAs during the 2015-2020 period chose to include gender-related provisions in their new agreement after not having done so in their previous agreement, and 20% of the countries that negotiated RTAs during the same period continue to negotiate gender-related provisions in their new agreements. In addition, 24% of the countries that signed RTAs during the 2015-2020 period have incorporated either the same or a higher number of types of gender-related provisions in their new agreements compared to their previous ones.

The bulk of the trade and gender literature focuses on the effect of trade liberalization on the employment and wage of women, in absolute terms and relative to men. Country-specific studies show mixed effects on gender inequality. For instance, Ederington et al. (2009) show, using plant-level data, that Colombia's trade liberalization episode between 1984 and 1991 resulted in proportionally more women being hired by Colombian plants. Similarly, Juhn et al. (2014) investigate the effect of tariff reductions associated with the North American Free Trade Agreement on gender inequality and find, using a panel of establishment-level data from Mexico, that tariff reductions caused new firms to enter the export market, modernize their technology and replace male blue-collar workers with female blue-collar workers. Since new technologies involve computerized production processes, the need for physically demanding skills decreases. As a result, the relative wage and employment of women improves in blue-collar tasks, but not in white-collar tasks. Black and Brainerd (2004) compare the change in the residual gender wage gap between 1977 and 1994 in concentrated versus competitive manufacturing industries in the United States, using the latter as a control for changes in the gender wage gap that are unrelated to competitive pressures due to trade liberalization, and find that increased competition through trade did contribute to the relative improvement in female wages in concentrated relative to competitive industries. Boler et al. (2015) investigate the link between the gender wage gap and exporting

using a matched employer-employee data set of firms in the Norwegian manufacturing sector and their full-time employees between 1996 and 2010, and find that the gender wage gap is higher in exporting firms than in non-exporters, and that the difference between the two narrows down with the changes in social attitudes. By contrast, using industry level data from 1981 to 1992, Seguino (2000) reports that as a consequence of trade, gender wage differentials widened in Taiwan but narrowed in Korea. She explains that, unlike Taiwan, government intervention in Korea prevented excessive outflows of capital in industries where women were overrepresented. Berik et al. (2004) use a panel dataset of residual wage gaps, trade ratios, and alternative measures of domestic concentration for Taiwan and Korea during the 1980s and 1990s and show that competition from trade openness in concentrated industries is positively associated with wage discrimination against women. Kucera (2001) studies the effects of trade liberalization on gender relative wages and employment for Germany and Japan using data from 1970 to 1996. He finds that trade openness negatively affects women's manufacturing employment in Japan but not in Germany, and explains this result by the fact that Germany has a higher trade intensity than Japan with non-OECD countries. Gupta (2021) studies the impact of the 1991 trade liberalization episode in India on the employment share of women, using a panel of establishments from the annual survey of industries. The author finds that establishments exposed to larger output tariff reductions and import competition reduced the share of female workers, as establishments increased the number of shifts per worker that reduced women participation, because women in India are prohibited by law from working long hours and night shifts. For Egypt, Hendy and Zaki (2013), using a microsimulation analysis and some trade liberalization scenarios, show that, thanks to the expansion of textiles, garments, chemicals, and services, inequality decreases for urban and rural skilled men as well as skilled and unskilled women working in urban areas.

Evidence from cross-country data is also mixed. Wood (1991) finds that trade liberalization increases the relative demand for female labor in developing countries but not for developed ones. Oostendorp (2009) shows using a database with more than 80 countries for 1983 to 1999 that the gender wage gap decreases with trade in richer countries, with little evidence for poorer countries. In a sample of 35 countries from 1960 to 1985, Tejani and Milberg (2010) study the effects of trade liberalization on the female share of employment in manufacturing of 60 high-income developed countries and middle-income developing countries over the period 1985 to 2006, and find that the relative employment of women increased in middle-income countries but decreased in the high-income ones. Wamboye and Seguino (2015) find for a panel 38 Sub-Saharan African countries for the period 1991–2010 that trade liberalization has gendered employment effects, with the direction depending on the structure of the economy. For example, trade openness has a negative effect on women's absolute and relative employment in non-mineral non-oil exporters, and a positive effect in non-oil mineral exporters.

Although the literature on the effect of trade liberalization on gender equality is extensive, the impact of gender-related provisions in RTA on gender equality in general, and women empowerment through leadership in particular, is missing. Some countries or economic blocs proceed to the assessment of the gender impact of trade agreements ex-ante, while negotiating the agreement, to help add/amend gender provisions to achieve specific gender targets. For instance, the Gender-Based Analysis Plus (GBA+) tool developed by Canada as an expanded economic impact assessment helped identify opportunities for adding new gender-related provisions in the case of the Canada-Mercosur FTA. Another example is the sustainability impact assessment (SIA)

conducted by the European Union (EU) during the negotiations of the EU-Chile trade agreement, that suggested including gender equality and support for women in the preamble and objectives of the modernized agreement so as to help women seize opportunities that the agreement offers. It called for mainstreaming gender issues into core trade disciplines such as trade in services, public procurement, and investment, and for including clear and measurable targets on women's rights into the trade and gender provisions (UNCTAD 2022).

The lack of empirical evidence of gender-related provisions in RTA comes from the fact that the actual inclusion of gender provisions in trade agreements is a relatively new phenomenon for many countries and the data required to conduct such empirical analysis is limited. An exception is the work of Mourela and Semaan (2018) who use a household survey to evaluate the impact of the 1999 Bilateral Textile Agreement between Cambodia and the United States (CUSBTA) on both the gender wage gap and discrimination, and find a statistically significant reduction of the gender wage gap in the textile sector that can be attributed to the CUSBTA.

Against this background, the present paper is the first, to our knowledge, to assess the impact of gender-related provisions on a particular aspect of gender inequality, namely women empowerment through leadership, using firm-level data for a sample including developed and developing countries. The use of firm-level data will help tackle under-explored aspects of gender inequality at the plant level, by looking at the difference in the managerial and ownership status between the two genders. We use the World Bank's Enterprise Surveys Database that offers an expansive array of economic data on 195,000 firms in 155 countries in 56 manufacturing and services sectors. We capture women empowerment at the firm level by 2 dependent variables, namely whether the owner or the manager are females. . Our main variables of interest are the number of gender-related provisions in the RTA. We use the World Trade Organization (WTO) Database on gender-related provisions in RTA, and differentiate between the types of RTAs (extra-regional vs. intra-regional) as well as the location of the gender-related provisions in RTAs, whether they appear in an article, in the preamble or in the annex. Our results show that the total number of RTAs, whether they are extra-regional or intra-regional, are positively associated with female empowerment, i.e. with a higher probability of the firm to be owned or managed by a female. Furthermore, the number of gender-related provisions in trade agreements, as well their location in articles and in annexes seem to matter in female empowerment through leadership. This result is robust whether the firm is an exporter, importer, or involved in the global value chain of the sector of interest. When differentiating countries by income level, we find that the positive link between gender-related provisions RTAs and women empowerment holds for developed countries only.

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes some stylized facts about gender inequality related to the ownership and management status of firms as well as gender-related provisions in FTA. Section 3 presents the methodology and the data. Section 4 is devoted to the discussion of the results and Section 5 concludes.

2. Stylized Facts

The inclusion of gender-related provisions in trade agreements is not a recent phenomenon. It dates back to the 1957 Treaty of Rome establishing the European Economic Community, where each member state was required to guarantee the principle of equal pay for women and men. The first RTA including gender provisions signed by developing countries came more than 25 years later, with the 1983 Treaty establishing the Economic Community of Central African States. The number of RTAs with gender-related provisions has increased globally over the years, with a rapid surge since 2016. By December 2020, 14% of all agreements analyzed included at least one provision explicitly referring to gender, of which 70% were negotiated between developed and developing economies, 16% between developing economies and 14% between developed (Monteiro, 2021).

Gender-related provisions could appear in different locations in the RTA text. They can be found in the preamble, stand-alone chapters, side agreements, specific provisions, cross-cutting provisions or chapters, protocols, declarations, arrangements or even in the annex of the trade agreement (Monteiro, 2021). The location of the gender provision can already give an idea about its importance and enforcement. Our sample shows that 96% of gender-related provisions appear in articles (or part of articles); while 1.90% and 1.75% appear respectively in the annex and the preamble of RTAs. By including gender-related provisions in RTAs, countries confirm their commitment to reduce gender inequality through trade policy. Gender inequality is not limited to wage differentials between men and women.

At the empowerment level, an under-explored dimension of gender discrimination resides in women's under-representation in leadership positions. Figure 1 shows the percentage of firms in our sample that are owned and managed by females. Indeed, 33.36% of the firms are owned by women while only 16% are female-managed. This stylized fact validates the common belief that women are under-represented in management and other leadership positions. Figure 1 also shows that the share of firms that are female-owned/managed does not significantly change when it is accounted for the export and import status of the firm, or for firms that are involved in the global value chain of the sector of interest.

Figure 2 differentiates between firms operating in developed vs. developing countries. It shows that 84% of firms included in our sample operate in developing countries. Among those firms, 32% are owned by a female and less than 16% have a woman as a top manager. By contrast, of the minority 16% of firms in developed countries included in our sample, more than 40% are female-owned and 17% are female-managed. Therefore, women's under-representation in leadership positions is more pronounced for developing countries. Furthermore, while female empowerment through ownership seems to be more frequent than female empowerment through management in both developed and developing countries, women representation in leadership positions in general (ownership/management) remains significantly lower than their male counterparts. This could be explained by various biases that obstruct women's career progression, such as gender norms and stereotypes, and financial constraints faced by female entrepreneurs (UNCTAD, 2022).

Figure 1: Percentage of Firms Owned/Managed by Females

Source: Constructed by the authors using the WBES database.

Figure 2: Percentage of Firms by Income Level

Source: Constructed by the authors using the WBES database.

Figures 3 and 4 examine, respectively, the percentage of female owners and managers by manufacturing and services sectors. It is noteworthy that, for both manufacturing and services, women empowerment is dominant through female ownership, rather than management, although the share of female owners in all manufacturing and services sectors is below 50% except for “Pharmaceuticals & Medical Products”, “Textiles, Garments & Leather” and “Textiles, Garments, Leather & Paper” where the share of female owners stands at 57%, 52% and 50% respectively. Sectors will the lowest share of female ownership include: “Machinery & Equipment, Electronics

& Vehicles”, “Motor Vehicles & Transport Equipment”, and “Retail & IT”. Except for “Pharmaceuticals & Medical Products” and “Garments” where respectively 36.36% and 31.93% of managers are females, the gap in female and male managerial positions is appalling in manufacturing sectors. Indeed, the share of female managers is generally below 20%, and this share is the highest in sectors like “Wood Products & Furniture” (20.58%), “Textiles & Garments” (18.83%), “Electronics & Communications Equipment” (16.36%) and “Manufacturing” (16%). The lowest representation of female managers is in sectors like “Machinery & Equipment, Electronics & Vehicles” (1.89%), “Wood products, Furniture, Paper & Publishing” (2.72%) and “Basic Metals & Metal Products” (3.89%).

While female ownership is more dominant in manufacturing, services sectors demonstrate a higher representation of female managers relative to manufacturing sectors. In fact, some services sectors show a share of female managers around 30% such as “Accommodation”, “Retail” (25.26%), “Hospitality & Tourism” (24.89%) and “Hotels & Restaurants” (24.61%). Others have a very low share of female managers, such as: “Wholesale & Retail” (4.41%), “Services of Motor Vehicles/Wholesale” (6.07%) and “Transport” (6.78%).

Figure 3: Percentage of Firms Owned/Managed by Females in Manufacturing Sectors

Source: Constructed by the authors using the WBES database.

Figure 4: Percentage of Firms Owned/Managed by Females in Services Sectors

Source: Constructed by the authors using the WBES database.

What story does the data tell about women empowerment in the presence and absence of gender-related provisions in trade agreements? Figures 5 and 6 show the association between the inclusion of gender provisions in different parts of trade agreements and women empowerment. Three important facts emerge. First, the share of female management/ownership increases when gender provisions are apparent in RTAs. For instance, the share of female ownership increases from 11% of firms to 22% when the agreements (intra or extra-regional agreements) includes a gender-related provision. Second, the location of the provision matters. Indeed, when the provisions are part of an article, the share of female owned /managed firms is higher than when the provisions are part of the preamble or the annex. This can be attributed by the enforceability of the provision given that the preamble is an introduction to agreement, not the agreement itself. Third, female ownership and management is generally higher in intra-regional agreements, then extra-regional one. This is primarily driven by intra-regional agreements signed between developed economies.

Figure 5: Female vs. Male Owned Firms and RTAs with vs. without Gender Provisions

Source: Constructed by the authors using the WBES database.

Figure 6: Female vs. Male Managed Firms and RTAs with vs. without Gender Provisions (GP)

Source: Constructed by the authors using the WBES database.

3. Methodology and Data

To understand the impact of gender-related provisions in RTAs on women empowerment, we account for the stylized facts presented in the previous section as well as plant characteristics that the literature found to affect gender inequality at the firm level. As highlighted so far in the paper, we tackle an under-explored aspect of gender inequality at the plant level, namely the difference in the managerial and ownership status between males and females in the firm. Therefore, we estimate the following Probit models:

$$Owner_{ijst} = a1 X_{ijst} + a2 Gend.Prov_{jt} + cd + sd + yd + v_{ijst} \quad (1)$$

$$Manager_{ijst} = a1 X_{ijst} + a2 Gend.Prov_{jt} + cd + sd + yd + v_{ijst} \quad (2)$$

The dependent variable in equation (1), $Owner_{ijst}$, is a binary variable that takes the value of 1 if the firm i in country j in sector s at time t is owned by a female, and 0 otherwise. Similarly, the dependent variable in equation (2), $Manager_{ijst}$, is a binary variable that takes the value of 1 if the firm i in country j in sector s at time t is managed by a female, and 0 otherwise.

X_{ijst} is a vector of plant-characteristics that are thought to affect gender inequality such as firm age (Pradhan, 2006), firm size (Pradhan, 2006 and Juhn et al., 2014), capital intensity (Pradhan, 2006; Juhn et al., 2014), R&D intensity (Pradhan, 2006; Juhn et al., 2014), the import of foreign technology (Pradhan, 2006), the share of foreign ownership (Juhn et al., 2014) and the share of government ownership, as well as the location of the firm (Gupta, 2021).

According to Pradhan (2006), younger firms can be assumed to have relatively less gender differences in employment than firms that have been in business for longer, mainly due rising women literacy in recent years and lessening of social restrictions on women's participation in employment. Therefore, we expect a higher probability for younger firms to be managed or owned by a female.

Pradhan (2006) also argues that large size firms are expected to be leaders in innovation with sufficient financial resources to employ more skilled workers. Therefore, the effect of firm size could negatively affect women workers embodying relatively lower skills. However, since a managerial position requires skilled workers, we expect firm size to be positively linked to the probability of a female to become a manager. The effect of firm size on female ownership could be difficult to predict, as it could depend on whether the female entrepreneur has the necessary skills that will make her successful in developing the firm, as well as on the financial constraints faced by her when it comes to access to capital in order to expand the firm's operations.

Juhn et al. (2014) highlights that the introduction of computerized production processes has lowered the need for physically demanding skills and has therefore favored women in certain occupations. Technology is represented by two variables: R&D intensity and the import of foreign technology. We expect those variables to be positively linked to the probability of the firm to be managed/owned by a female.

The share of foreign ownership is expected to positively affect women empowerment, due to the increased awareness of the importance of gender equality in developed countries. Furthermore, we believe it is reasonable to expect that firms with state ownership are more prone to employ women, and to be managed by women, as limited working hours in government firms are attractive for females who can also find time for their household duties.

Our variables of interest are those related to gender provisions in RTAs: the total number of gender provisions in country j 's agreements $AllProvisions_{jt}$, the number of gender provisions in country j 's agreements appearing in articles $Articles_{jt}$, those appearing in the preamble $Preamble_{jt}$, and those appearing in the annex $Annex_{jt}$. RTA_{jt} is the total number of RTA for country j at time t , $RTA-intra_{jt}$ and $RTA-extra_{jt}$ are the country i 's number of intra-regional and extra-regional trade agreements respectively.

Two empirical remarks are worthy to be mentioned. First, standard errors are clustered by country and by sector as all firms operating in the same country and the same sector face the same gender provisions in trade agreements. Second, all regressions are run using a Probit (given that our dependent variables are binary) and a linear probability model (as it gives elasticities).

The regressions are extended in different ways: First, we investigate whether the export status of the firm affects the probability of that firm to be owned/managed by a female. Indeed, gender-related provisions included in RTAs are expected to affect mostly firms that are engaged in international trade. Therefore, we run the regressions for two sub-samples: a sub-sample consisting of exporting firms, and another of importing firms. Second, we investigate whether the involvement of the firm in global value chains affects the probability of that firm to be owned/managed by a female. Accordingly, we only include in our sample those firms that are importer and exporter in the same sector. Finally, we split our sample to distinguish between firms operating in developed vs. developing countries. The rationale resides in the fact that developed countries have deployed over the years much more effort than developing countries in tackling issues related to gender inequality in general, and in empowering women in particular. Furthermore, as mentioned earlier in the text, developed countries have started two decades earlier than developing countries in acknowledging the important effect of trade policy on gender equality by incorporating gender-related provisions in trade agreements. Indeed, the first agreement between developing countries incorporating gender-related provisions was the 1957 Treaty of Rome establishing the European Economic Community, while the first RTA between developing countries including gender provisions came more than 25 years later, with the 1983 Treaty establishing the Economic Community of Central African States (Monteiro, 2021).

Our data is collected from two main sources. First, firms' data come from the World Bank Enterprise Surveys³ that offers an expansive array of economic data on 195,000 firms in 155 countries operating in 56 manufacturing and services sectors. Formal (registered) companies with 5 or more employees are targeted for interview. Firms with 100% government/state ownership are not eligible to participate in an Enterprise Survey. The surveys capture important characteristics of firms such as age, legal status, domestic vs. foreign ownership, internationally recognized quality certification, and cover a broad range of business environment topics including access to finance, corruption, infrastructure, crime, competition, trade, technology and innovation, gender

³<https://www.enterprisesurveys.org/en/enterprisesurveys>

participation and performance measures. The manufacturing and services sectors are the primary business sectors of interest. This corresponds to firms classified with ISIC codes 15-37, 45, 50-52, 55, 60-64, and 72 (ISIC Rev.3.1). Services firms include construction, retail, wholesale, hotels, restaurants, transport, storage, communications, and IT. Second, data on gender-related provisions in RTA come from the WTO Database on gender provisions in RTAs that maps more than 300 gender provisions included in more than 100 regional trade agreements, representing almost a third of RTAs currently in force and notified to the WTO by members. The provisions can be filtered by parties and regions, as well as by type of gender issues addressed, the implementation instruments provided and their location in the RTA. Information about the mechanisms for the monitoring and evaluation of the provisions or the dispute settlement is also provided. Table 1 summarizes the descriptive statistics of the variables used in the regressions.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. dev.	Min	Max
Female top manager	151,188	.1581276	.3648618	0	1
Female owner	170,130	.3335978	.4714993	0	1
Global value chain	180,067	.193167	.394784	0	1
Privately owned	180,067	.1035281	.3046483	0	1
Importer	180,067	.6733383	.4689937	0	1
Exporter	180,067	.2470469	.4312955	0	1
Foreign Technology	180,067	.1049054	.3064323	0	1
R&D	180,067	.1430801	.3501555	0	1
Ln foreign ownership	177,109	.4466128	1.308169	0	4.61512
Ln gov. ownership	177,177	.0508276	.4306891	0	4.61512
Main city	114,514	1.571738	.499781	0	2
Size	180,067	1.721559	.7641371	1	3
Ln age	179,893	2.719068	1.007728	0	7.615791
All provisions	180,067	13.71699	27.63352	0	96
Annex	180,067	.2600199	.626909	0	3
Preamble	180,067	.2416878	.5000069	0	2
Articles	180,067	13.21529	26.80757	0	91
All agreements	180,067	5.063254	9.815441	0	34
Intra-regional	180,067	2.233974	4.036492	0	14
Extra-regional	180,067	2.82928	5.878722	0	20

Source: Authors' own elaboration.

4. Results

The regressions results are summarized in Tables 2 to 5. Due to the large number of control variables and variables of interest, we first display in Table 2 the results for the control variables. First, Table 2 shows that the age of the firm is negatively linked to the probability of the manager of the firm to be a female, with the age coefficient being significant. This finding is in line with Pradhan (2006) who argues that younger firms might have relatively less gender differences in employment due to rising literacy in recent years. However, age is found to be positively associated with the probability of the owner of the firm to be female, although the sign of the age coefficient is not significant.

Second, an increase in the share of government ownership in the firm is significantly linked to a decrease in the probability of the manager to be a female, and to an increase in the probability of the owner to be female. This result is surprising as we might expect that firms with state ownership are more prone to employ and to be managed by women, as limited working hours in government firms are attractive for women who can also find time for their household duties. A possible explanation of this result could be the rigidity of firms with state ownership when it comes to the adaptation to new social norms involving women inclusion in managerial positions where the female manager will be involved in the decision making process. By contrast, a female owner does not have to be directly involved in the decision making process.

Third, the location of the firm in the main city decreases the probability of the firm's manager/owner to be a female. This can be attributed to the abundance of males and discrimination against females in large agglomerations and thus their higher probability to be an owner or a manager of a firm.

Fourth, firms' size is negatively linked to the probability of the firm's manager to be a female. Indeed, the probability of having a female manager decreases for large and medium firms relative to small firms, although the size coefficient is only significant for medium firms. This finding is contradictory with the work of Pradhan (2006). A possible explanation of this finding could be the lack of confidence in women capabilities to manage large firms, mainly in developing countries where gender discrimination seems to be dominant. By contrast, there is a positive association between firms' size and the probability of a female owner, although the size coefficient is only significant for large firms.

Finally, it is noteworthy that imports of foreign technology, R&D and the share of foreign ownership are not significant in explaining the management/ownership status of firms. Since the sign and significance of our control variables do not change across specifications, we discard them, for the sake of brevity, from all the subsequent tables and focus on the effect of our variables of interest⁴.

Table 3 displays the results of our variables of interest in the baseline regressions. It shows that the total number of agreements signed by the country, whether they are intra or extra-regional, are all positively linked to the probability of the firm to be managed/owned by a female. This result could be explained by the increasing number of agreements that are tackling the questions of gender equality and female empowerment. In addition, the number of provisions in those agreements is, as expected, positively associated with the female ownership/management status of the firm. Moreover, the location of the gender provision in the agreement seems to matter. Indeed, there is a significant positive association between those provisions appearing in articles and in annexes and the female ownership/management status of the firm, the coefficient of those appearing in the Preamble is however not significant, although being positive. Therefore, our results highlight the importance of tackling the question of women empowerment through trade policy.

⁴ The complete tables including all independent variables for the regressions are available upon request.

Table 2: Results with Control Variables

	Female Top Manager		Female Owner	
	LPM	Probit	LPM	Probit
Ln(Age)	-0.0171** (0.00826)	-0.0668** (0.0319)	0.0102 (0.0132)	0.0300 (0.0391)
Ln(Gov. Own)	-0.0249*** (0.00764)	-0.134** (0.0606)	0.0504*** (0.00729)	0.158*** (0.0284)
R&D	0.00834 (0.0260)	0.0437 (0.116)	0.00440 (0.0169)	0.0167 (0.0505)
Main city	-0.0238*** (0.00770)	-0.0876*** (0.0292)	-0.0574*** (0.0186)	-0.170*** (0.0518)
Ln(for. Own)	-0.00427 (0.00364)	-0.0167 (0.0161)	-0.00174 (0.00567)	-0.00432 (0.0161)
For. Tech.	-0.00396 (0.00747)	-0.0102 (0.0302)	-0.0276 (0.0259)	-0.0795 (0.0734)
Medium	-0.0251** (0.00987)	-0.101** (0.0424)	0.00763 (0.0115)	0.0223 (0.0348)
Large	-0.0263 (0.0173)	-0.0987 (0.0777)	0.0327** (0.0158)	0.102** (0.0506)
Constant	0.400*** (0.0335)	-0.376*** (0.140)	0.218** (0.0985)	-1.317*** (0.276)
Observations	112,501	112,466	110,842	110,842
R-squared	0.066		0.129	

Robust standard errors in parentheses, country, sector and year fixed effects are included in the regressions.

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Table 3: Baseline Regression – Probit Estimation

	Female Top Manager	Female Owner
Intra-regional	0.0207*** (0.00715)	0.0307** (0.0133)
Extra-regional	0.0341** (0.0149)	0.0599** (0.0235)
All agreements	0.0131*** (0.00487)	0.0205** (0.00852)
Articles	0.00529*** (0.00197)	0.00796** (0.00355)
Preamble	0.133 (0.103)	0.0246 (0.0848)
Annex	0.106** (0.0456)	0.243*** (0.0696)
All Provisions	0.00517*** (0.00189)	0.00786** (0.00338)

Robust standard errors in parentheses, *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Notes: (i) Each cell represents a regression. (ii) All controls and fixed effects in Table 2 are included in different regressions.

Since trade agreements are expected to affect firms involved in international trade, we divide our sample between exporting and importing firms in the sector of interest (columns 1 to 5 in Table 4). The sign and significance of our variables of interest are unchanged: all agreements signed by the country with its trading partners, whether intra or extra-regional, have a positive and significant coefficient. The total number of provisions, especially those appearing in annexes and articles still have a positive and significant coefficient. This shows that regardless of import/export status of the firm, the inclusion of gender provisions in trade agreements matters for women empowerment.

In Columns 6 and 7 of Table 4, we consider firms that are participating in the global value chain in the sector of interest. Those firms are expected to be affected by trade agreements through their engagement in international trade. We find that all trade agreements, whether intra or extra-regional, are positively linked to the probability of a firm to be managed/owned by a female, and the coefficients are mostly significant. In addition, the number of provisions included in agreements, and in particular those appearing in articles and annexes are positively associated with the management/ownership status of the firm.

Table 4: Probit Estimation by Import/Export Status

	Importers		Exporters		GVC	
	Female Manager	Female Owner	Female Manager	Female Owner	Female Manager	Female Owner
Intra-regional	0.0386*** (0.0105)	0.0288** (0.0123)	0.0521** (0.0209)	0.0322* (0.0190)	0.0656** (0.0307)	0.0270 (0.0166)
Extra-regional	0.0742*** (0.0200)	0.0582*** (0.0221)	0.0974** (0.0410)	0.0733** (0.0365)	0.135** (0.0596)	0.0623* (0.0323)
All agreements	0.0257*** (0.00694)	0.0195** (0.00792)	0.0342** (0.0140)	0.0226* (0.0126)	0.0445** (0.0204)	0.0191* (0.0110)
Articles	0.0103*** (0.00277)	0.00751** (0.00326)	0.0138** (0.00570)	0.00910* (0.00516)	0.0180** (0.00826)	0.00771* (0.00450)
Preamble	-0.159* (0.0954)	-0.121 (0.112)	-0.205 (0.177)	-0.286 (0.259)	-0.511** (0.230)	-0.215 (0.178)
Annex	0.189*** (0.0688)	0.206*** (0.0655)	0.289** (0.127)	0.235** (0.103)	0.352* (0.188)	0.201** (0.0937)
All Provisions	0.00989*** (0.00271)	0.00734** (0.00312)	0.0133** (0.00550)	0.00881* (0.00493)	0.0173** (0.00798)	0.00747* (0.00431)

Robust standard errors in parentheses, *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Notes: (i) Each cell represents a regression. (ii) All controls and fixed effects in Table 2 are included in different regressions.

Table 5 distinguishes between countries based on their income level. Indeed, developed countries have been more engaged than developing ones in achieving gender equality over years. In particular, developed countries have started to include an increasing number of gender provisions in their trade agreements two decades before developing countries. The results show that the coefficients of all our variables of interest are positive and significant in explaining the probability of a firm to be managed by a female for developed countries only, without any effect on the female ownership status. This result is expected as developed countries have been considering gender provisions in their trade agreements for a certain time, while developing

countries have only started to include such provisions in their trade agreements recently. In addition, all types of provisions, whether they appear in the preamble, in articles and in annexes, are positively linked to the female management status of the firm. However, those provisions do not appear to explain the probability of a firm to be owned by a female. This result can be attributed to the fact gender provisions can improve women empowerment at the operational level as they might facilitate their participation in trade activities. Female managers are more involved in the day-to-day activities.

Table 5: Probit Estimation by Income Level

	Developed Countries		Developing Countries	
	Female Top Manager	Female Owner	Female Top Manager	Female Owner
Intra-regional	0.0201*** (0.00327)	-0.00898 (0.00748)	0.0117 (0.00956)	0.00845 (0.0220)
Extra-regional	0.0403*** (0.00654)	-0.0180 (0.0150)	0.0231 (0.0191)	0.0213 (0.0422)
All agreements	0.0134*** (0.00218)	-0.00599 (0.00499)	0.00793 (0.00644)	0.00629 (0.0146)
Articles	0.00549*** (0.000892)	-0.00245 (0.00204)	0.00298 (0.00263)	0.00149 (0.00584)
Preamble	0.218*** (0.0173)	0.0872*** (0.0240)	-0.108 (0.0924)	0.207 (0.209)
Annex	0.121*** (0.0196)	-0.0539 (0.0449)	0.00982 (0.0585)	0.186 (0.129)
All Provisions	0.00525*** (0.000853)	-0.00234 (0.00195)	0.00274 (0.00253)	0.00191 (0.00565)

Robust standard errors in parentheses, *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Notes: (i) Each cell represents a regression. (ii) All controls and fixed effects in Table 2 are included in different regressions.

In sum, our results show that: first, the total number of gender-related provisions included in a country's in RTAs, and those specifically appearing in articles or annexes, are positively associated with women empowerment, through female ownership and management of the firms. Second, this finding holds for the firm whether it is an exporter, importer or engaged in the global value chain. Third, the inclusion of gender-related provisions in RTAs seems to be more effective on female representation in managerial positions only in developed countries.

5. Conclusion and Policy Implications

The current paper investigates the effect of gender-related provisions included in RTAs on under-explored aspects of gender inequality at the plant level, namely the under-representation of women in ownership and managerial positions of the firm. This topic is timely and critical due to the hike in the number of RTAs with such provisions after 2016 and the increased the recognition of gender issues in trade policymaking.

Using the World Bank's Enterprise Surveys Database., we capture women empowerment at the firm level. The explanatory variables of our interest include the number of gender-related provisions in the RTA, as well as the location of the gender-related provisions in RTAs, whether they appear in an article, in the preamble or in the annex. Our results show that the total number of RTAs, whether they are extra-regional or intra-regional, are positively associated with female empowerment, i.e. with a higher probability of the firm to be owned or managed by a female. Furthermore, the number of gender-related provisions in trade agreements, as well their location in articles and in annexes seem to matter in female empowerment through leadership. This result is robust whether the firm is an exporter, importer, or involved in the global value chain of the sector of interest. When differentiating countries by income level, we find that the positive link between gender-related provisions RTAs and women empowerment holds for developed countries only.

Is the increased inclusion of gender-related provisions in trade agreements an effective way of promoting women empowerment? Our results suggest that trade policy could have its positive effects and help streamline gender in trade negotiations. Therefore, policymakers are encouraged to move away from a gender-blind trade policy to a gender-aware policy by increasing the recognition of gender issues in trade policymaking through a wider coverage of gender-related provisions in trade agreements. To enhance the positive outcomes of a gender-aware trade policy, it would be beneficial that women's groups and other civil society representatives are more involved in the negotiation, design, and implementation of trade agreements. This would help ensure that trade policy is more responsive to women's needs and gender equality concerns.

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Appendix

Table A1: List of countries.

Afghanistan	China	Grenada	Mali	Rwanda	Uruguay
Albania	Colombia	Guatemala	Malta	Samoa	Uzbekistan
Angola	Congo	Guinea	Mauritania	Senegal	Vanuatu
Antigua and Barbuda	Costa Rica	Guinea	Mauritius	Serbia	Venezuela
Argentina	Croatia	Bissau	Mexico	Sierra Leone	Vietnam
Armenia	Cyprus	Guyana	Micronesia	Slovak Republic	West Bank And Gaza
Austria	Czech Republic	Honduras	Moldova	Slovenia	Yemen
Azerbaijan	Côte d'Ivoire	Hungary	Mongolia	Solomon Islands	Zambia
Bahamas	DRC	India	Montenegro	South Africa	Zimbabwe
Bangladesh	Denmark	Indonesia	Morocco	South Sudan	
Barbados	Djibouti	Iraq	Mozambique	Spain	
Belarus	Dominica	Ireland	Myanmar	Sri Lanka	
Belgium	Dominican Republic	Israel	Namibia	St Kitts and Nevis	
Belize	Ecuador	Italy	Nepal	St Lucia	
Benin	Egypt	Jamaica	Netherlands	St Vincent and Grenadines	
Bhutan	El Salvador	Jordan	Nicaragua	Sudan	
Bolivia	Eritrea	Kazakhstan	Niger	Suriname	
Bosnia and Herzegovina	Estonia	Kenya	Nigeria	Sweden	
Botswana	Eswatini	Kosovo	North Macedonia	Tajikistan	
Brazil	Ethiopia	Kyrgyz Republic	Pakistan	Tanzania	
Bulgaria	Fiji	Lao PDR	Panama	Thailand	
Burkina Faso	Finland	Latvia	Papua New Guinea	Timor-Leste	
Burundi	France	Lebanon	Paraguay	Togo	
Cambodia	Gabon	Lesotho	Peru	Tonga	
Cameroon	Gambia	Liberia	Philippines	Trinidad and Tobago	
Cape Verde	Georgia	Lithuania	Poland	Tunisia	
Central African Republic	Germany	Luxembourg	Portugal	Türkiye	
Chad	Ghana	Madagascar	Romania	Uganda	
Chile	Greece	Malawi	Russia	Ukraine	
		Malaysia			